

A Study on the Globalization of Indian Textile Industry

*by Beena Soreng, Resource Person,
Department of B.Com (Co-op. Mgt.),
M.G. Govt. College, Mayabunder - 744204*

&

*Mohd. Mohsin, Resource Person,
Department of B.Com (Co-op. Mgt.),
M.G. Govt. College, Mayabunder - 744204*

Introduction :

Globalization is a huge term. It has come to be used in every industry and in every geographical location. It has influenced trade and commerce of all types. It has brought countries together. There was no way warring countries could be united except for by trade. Globalization has made this possible! Today, one can get Swiss watches, French champagnes, Chinese noodles, and other specialized items in every corner of the Earth.

The initiation and development of globalization and Indian textile industry took place simultaneously in the 1990s. The Indian textile industry, until the economic liberalization of Indian economy was predominantly an unorganized industry. The economic liberalization of Indian economy in the early 1990s led to stupendous growth of this Indian industry. The Indian textile industry is one of the largest textile industries in the world and India earns around 27 percent of the foreign exchange from exports of textiles and its related products. Further, globalization of India textile industry has seen a paradigm increase in the 'total

industrial production' factor of this Industry, which presently stands at 14 percent. Furthermore, the contribution of the Indian textile industry towards the gross domestic product (GDP) of India is around 3 percent and the numbers are steadily increasing. The process of globalization and Indian textile industry development was the effect of rapid acceptance of 'open market' policy by the developing countries, much in the lines of the developed countries of the world.

Globalization of the Indian textile sector was the cumulative effect of the following factors :

- Huge textile production capacity
- Efficient multi-fiber raw material manufacturing capacity
- Large pool of skilled and cheap work force
- Entrepreneurial skills
- Huge export potential
- Large domestic market
- Very low import content
- Flexible textile manufacturing systems

The Indian textile industry consist of the following sectors :

- Filament Yarn Industry
- Cotton Textile Industry
- Jute Industry
- Silk and Silk Textile Industry
- Wool & Woolen Industry
- Power loom Sector
- Man-made Fiber

India's Position in Global Textiles and Clothing Industry :

- India's position in the World Textiles Economy Second largest producer of raw cotton.
- Second largest producer of cotton yarn.
- Second largest producer of cellulosic fibre/yarn.
- Second largest producer of silk.
- Fourth largest producer of synthetic fibre/yarn.
- Largest producer of jute.

The Indian textiles industry is one of the largest textiles industries in the world. With the abolition of quotas in 2005, Indian Textiles and Apparel exports grew by 19 percent to reach US\$ 17 billion in 2005-06. Indian exports increased in both the major destinations of US and EU.

Measuring Globalization :

Globalization has many faces. It deals with the increase in values and volumes of trade in goods and services among countries, which generally result from reducing tariffs, quotas and other barriers to trade, The associated FDI aimed at facilitating this process is also a key factor. It also deals with the development and spread of technologies, especially Information and Telecommunication Technologies, which allow access to information all over the world, and to connect with production, distribution and knowledge networks, rapidly increasing the potential for development around the globe. Furthermore, it also deals with international migration between developing and developed countries, and among themselves, which changes the economic relations and structures among and within countries.

All these faces can affect the behavior and the structure of labor markets within a country. In particular, depending on which of these features are more important for a particular country, and the particular (idiosyncratic) characteristics of the country that determines how it is prepared (or not) to take advantages of the new opportunities and challenges posed by globalization, will lead to a different impact.

An approximate number of textile manufacturing companies operating in India are given below -

Table No. 1

Sl. No.	Particulars	No. of Companies
1.	Badges, emblems ribbons and allied products	175
2.	Bed covers, curtains, cushions and other draperies	2471
3.	Carpets and rugs	270
4.	Embroidery and embroidered garments, made ups and furnishing	848
5.	Fabrics and textiles	3013
6.	Yarns and threads	1201
7.	Jute products	337
8.	Kids apparel and garments	1052
9.	Ladies apparel and garments	2932
10.	Men's apparel and garments	2936
11.	Miscellaneous garments, textile and leather accessories	1658
12.	Wool, woolen garments, blankets and accessories	468
13.	Textile chemicals, dyeing and finishing chemicals	239

Source : Secondary Data

Factors that give countries an advantage :

In an assessment of the competitiveness of foreign clothing and textiles suppliers to the US market (US International Trade Commission, 2004), the US

International Trade Commission identified seven factors that could potentially provide countries with a competitive advantage.

- 1. Business climate and infrastructure :** Buyers are likely to concentrate on countries that are politically and financially stable, as well as compliant with acceptable labour standards. Infrastructure supporting the buying process (e.g. telecommunications, ease of import and export documentation, test centres) is also critical.
- 2. Proximity to markets :** Reliable delivery and lead times are increasingly important, making it difficult for firms in distant locations to satisfy customer requirements.
- 3. Market access :** Although quotas have been removed, tariffs still remain.
- 4. Labour and management :** To be competitive a country needs a skilled (or trainable), inexpensive and productive labour force. Low labour costs alone are insufficient.
- 5. Raw material inputs :** Availability of cost-competitive quality fabrics and trim in a country or region is important because it affects production lead times and reliability, as well as the rapid provision of samples before order placement. If fabrics are not available locally, then shipping times and other logistics problems can affect lead times and cost, thus increasing buyer risks.
- 6. Level of service provided and reliability of supplier :** The buyer driven nature of the textiles clothing value chain has forced suppliers to be more responsive to buyer demands. As customers begin to reduce the number of suppliers, they are likely to use those which are competitively priced and flexible, offering full-package services.
- 7. Domestic demand :** The growth in domestic demand in developing countries, particularly in Asia, may result in these countries supplying greater proportions of production to the domestic market.

Conclusion :

The overall growth of the Indian textile industry can be attributed to the globalization. Today, the Indian textile industry employs around 35 million personnel directly and it accounts for 21 percent of the total employment generated in the economy. Globalization of the Indian textile industry has also facilitated introduction of modern and efficient manufacturing machineries and techniques in the Indian textile sector. Globalization has had many advantages. But it also has this drawback. It has led to the emergence of sweat shops. A new kind of exploitation has been given birth to. Corporate giants are cashing in on the poverty of the developing countries and making the already developed countries poorer. Thus, much of India's economic growth is largely dependent on textile manufacturing and exports.

References :

1. Beck, Ulrich (2000) : What is Globalization? Cambridge : Polity.
2. Beynon, J. and Dunkerley, D. (eds.) (2000) : Globalization A Reader, London : Athlone Press.
3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Textile_industry
4. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Globalization>